

ENGLISH GRAMMAR TEST SOLVING THROUGH NLP STRATEGIES TO AID APPLICANTS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. The article reveals several problems that applicants encounter while solving English grammar tests to enter national universities of Uzbekistan. It is devoted to finding solutions to such issues by illustrating easy NLP strategies on some topics.

Keywords. *NLP, non-finite forms, agreement, relative clause*

Аннотация. В статье раскрывается ряд проблем, с которыми сталкиваются абитуриенты при решении тестов по грамматике английского языка для поступления в национальные вузы Узбекистана. Она посвящена поиску решений таких проблем, иллюстрируя простые стратегии НЛП по некоторым темам.

Ключевые слова. *НЛП, неличные формы глагола, соглашение, придаточное предложение*

Annotatsiya. Maqolada abituriyentlar O'zbekiston oliy o'quv yurtlariga kirishda ingliz tili grammatikasi testlarini yechishda duch keladigan bir qancha muammolar ochib berilgan. Ushbu maqola ba'zi mavzularda oson NLP strategiyalarini ko'rsatish orqali bunday muammolarga yechim topishga bag'ishlangan.

Kalit so'zlar. *NLP, fe'llarning shaxsi noma'lum shakllari, moslashuv, ergashgan qo'shma gaplar*

INTRODUCTION. It is known that English is being learnt for different purposes. Someone is learning it for business, someone for travelling or someone for taking an exam. While learning, ones use a variety of books and instructions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Here I can state that “English For Tests” is a special instructional book for the ones who are going to prepare to enter the universities independently. Although majority of applicants know the rules of grammar perfectly, answer questions orally, they tend to have some problems solving grammar tests. With the help of this book, everything will be EASY.

First, the structure of tests, the way of solving them EASILY are explained in EASY strategies. Second, tests related to the topics, the strategies of which are illustrated, are given too, which gives you an opportunity to solve sample tests immediately. Third, another problem that applicants face is TEXT. Some phrases, such as –translate the text; - according the passage; -all the statements are TRUE, EXCEPT; may frighten applicants. There is no need to be frightened any more. If you follow the strategies in the book, everything will be EASY. Atikns, Hailom, Nuru, Ellis, Ur and Girma were those who did

their best to show how important Grammar is and how crucial it is to find effective ways to enhance Grammar.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Now we will depict some samples of strategies in the article of ours. Tenses – everyone who is learning English has been familiar with this topic and the functions of it. English learners generally know which tense is used for regular actions, which is utilized for temporary situations and majority of applicants have solved the tests related to the topic. So we are not going to remind them any more here. We are to grab your attention to the weak points that have been left carelessly.

The options of the topic test of tenses are often structured by the formulas like: A) have gone B) was going C) had gone D) went and such tests are frequently given with conjunctions. The points that we have to take into consideration while solving tense tests:

✓ One has to search for any time conjunction existence within the question as it helps to cross out wrong answers. First, Future tenses are never used after time conjunctions.

If / Until / Till / After / When / Before ~~WILL—SHALL~~

Second, tense agreement is remembered here (Past – Past, Future – Present, Present – Present). If here is either of these circumstances, they are crossed out.

✓ Adverbs of time should be taken as key elements to solve the tense tests. Some applicants tend to confuse the concept of ASPECT (Simple, Continuous, Perfect, Perfect Continuous) with the concept of TENSE (Present, Past, Future, Future in the Past).

For instance, yesterday – Past tense + by – Aspect of Perfect = by yesterday – Past Perfect tense. Once the key word of the tense is found, an applicant will be able to move to the key element of aspect.

Keywords of ASPECT: every day/month/week/year, often, frequently, regularly, habitually, never, hardly, for, just, since, all, by, etc.

Keywords of TENSE: today, yesterday, tomorrow, last year, next year, etc.

✓ Logics, which contains suffixes of the tenses, the voice (Active or Passive) and functions, is considered as the last element to solve the tests of tenses.

Table 1

Test: The bacteria in milk is destroyed when it...to at least 62 C.

- | | |
|-------------------|--------------|
| A. will be heated | B. is heated |
| C. be heated | D. heated |

Analysis: First, try to find any conjunction in the question (when) and remember the rules of conjunctions, such as Future tense is not used after it and cross out (A). Tense agreement is also important (is destroyed – present tense and is never used with past). (D) is crossed out. (B) and (C) are left. There is no formula of (C) in Tenses.

Correct answer: (B) (Passive voice)

Below shall we show a number of confusing situations with key words and conjunctions:

Table 2

First Last	The first time The last time	It's the first time It's the last time
They are key words of Past Simple.	They are not key words. They are conjunctions of Past Simple + Past Simple	They are key words of Present Perfect and are located at the beginning of the sentence. !!! It <i>was</i> the first time It <i>was</i> the last time + Past Perfect
S + first/last + V2(ed)	The first time S + V2(ed), S + V2(ed)	It's the first time S + have/has V3(ed)
Roger last <u>saw</u> Helen last week.	The last time Roger <u>saw</u> Helen, he <u>didn't recognize</u> her.	It is the last time Roger <u>has seen</u> Helen. It was the last time Roger <u>had seen</u> Helen.

Just / just now

Just –Key word of Perfect (aspect). Most of the applicants are opt to think that it belongs to Present Perfect. No, it is the key element of all Perfects. If it belongs to Past Perfect, it is used with any element (conjunction or adverb) of Past tense.

S + have/ has + just + V3(ed)

S + had + just + V3(ed) when S + V2(ed)

Example: I have just bought this coat.

I had just bought the coat when you called me.

Just now –Key word of Past Simple.

S + V2(ed) + just now.

Example: I bought the coat just now.

Still – Key element of both tenses and aspects.

Example: I still love you.

I am still waiting for you.

I have been still waiting for you.

I will still be in Tashkent at this time next week.

In Past Tenses, it is used with conjunctions and adverbs of time.

Example: I was still waiting for you when you phoned me.

It was 5 a.m. But I was still waiting for you.

Providing this key word is used in Perfect, it comes after SUBJECT and in negative sentences. In Past Perfect Tense it is utilized with either conjunction or adverb of Past tense.

Example: Bunyod still hasn’t changed his mind.

Bunyod still hadn’t changed his mind when the inspector showed him that photo.

Table 3

<p>Before – Key word of Perfect and comes at the end of the sentence</p>	<p>Before –Conjunction Before S + V2(ed), S + had V3(ed). S + had + V3(ed) before S + V2(ed).</p> <p>Before S + V(s,es), S + will have V3(ed) S + will have V3(ed) before S + V(s,es)</p> <p>Before S + V(s,es), S + will V1 S + will V1 before S + V(s,es)</p> <p>Before S + V(s,es), S + V(s,es).</p>
<p>It is the 1st time I’ve seen her. I have never seen her <i>before</i>.</p> <p>It was the 1st time I had seen her. I had never seen her <i>before</i>.</p>	<p>Before I did my housework, I had watched TV.</p> <p>Before Lola comes, I’ll have done my housework.</p> <p>Before Lola comes, I’ll phone you.</p> <p>Before Kamola observes something, she takes a photo of it.</p>

CONCLUSION. The findings of the current article may encourage all instructors, teachers, administrators and textbook designers to pay more attention to English grammar. According to the findings of the current study, several implications should be pointed out, first, EFL learners may benefit from the findings, by spending more time and asking for more tutorial sessions to facilitate the consolidation of difficult features. Second, when both teachers and students are aware of this hierarchy of difficulty, they may spend more time explaining and offering examples, and may offer remedies and provide some additional comments through different activities to facilitate the mastering of difficult features. In addition, material developers and EFL curriculum could also benefit from the

findings. They should provide sufficient guidance and help in the curriculum documents and in the teachers’ books showing how these difficulties could be addressed in planning their classroom activities. They should include materials with an emphasis on the more difficult features. Additionally, providing drills and exercises which specifically address features that are more difficult might affect the consolidation of grammar.

We have shown several strategies to solve the tests of tenses. There are a number of tips in every topic that can be helpful to you. In any test solving strategy, the most important point is that NEVER TRY to find a correct answer, TRY to find a correct answer by crossing out wrong ones.

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